

Supplementary Table S1. Transposon mutagenesis screen results.

NR Well Location	Locus Tag	Gene Name	Gene Description	Gene Role
9-E1	VC2482	ilvH	acetolactate synthase III, small subunit	Amino acid biosynthesis
10-D1	VC0029	ilvE	branched-chain amino acid aminotransferase	Amino acid biosynthesis
9-E12	VCA0684	thiE	thiamin-phosphate pyrophosphorylase	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers
17-F8	VC0061	thiC	thiamin biosynthesis protein ThiC	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers
33-G10	VC1296	thiD	phosphomethylpyrimidine kinase	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers
12-E7	VC2481	serA	D-3-phosphoglycerate dehydrogenase	Amino acid biosynthesis
28-B11	VC2345	serB	phosphoserine phosphatase	Amino acid biosynthesis
28-H7	VC2363	thrB	homoserine kinase	Amino acid biosynthesis
33-G6	VC2362	thrC	threonine synthase	Amino acid biosynthesis
10-F1	VC1169	trpA	tryptophan synthase, alpha subunit	Amino acid biosynthesis
33-H10	VC1170	trpB	tryptophan synthase, beta subunit	Amino acid biosynthesis
34-C5	VC1174	trpE	anthranilate synthase component I	Amino acid biosynthesis
5-H6	VC0705	pheA	chorismate mutase/prephenate dehydratase	Amino acid biosynthesis
25-C3	VC0056	aroE	shikimate 5-dehydrogenase	Amino acid biosynthesis
9-B1	VC0149	epsC	general secretion pathway protein C	Protein fate
28-E3	VC2725	epsL	general secretion pathway protein L	Protein fate
33-E3	VC1709		zinc protease, insulinase family	Protein fate
1-F3	VC1181	cydD	transport ATP-binding protein CydD	Transport and binding proteins
12-G7	VC2270	ribE	riboflavin synthase, alpha subunit	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers
23-C6	VC2268	ribE	6,7-dimethyl-8-ribityllumazine synthase	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers
28-H2	VC0094	ubiA	4-hydroxybenzoate octaprenyltransferase	Biosynthesis of cofactors, prosthetic groups, and carriers
23-C8	VC2628	aroB	3-dehydroquinate synthase	Amino acid biosynthesis
5-A12	VC2414	aceE	pyruvate dehydrogenase, E1 component	Energy metabolism
32-A1	VC2413	aceF	pyruvate dehydrogenase, E2 component, dihydrolipoamide acetyltransferase	Energy metabolism
27-A7	VC2544	fbp	fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase	Energy metabolism
4-H4	VC0604	acnB	aconitate hydratase 2	Energy metabolism
26-A10	VC1487		conserved hypothetical protein	Hypothetical proteins
3-C8	VC0849		conserved hypothetical protein	Hypothetical proteins